

Integration of duck and jarwo super rice system in Riau Province as an alternative environmental friendly technology on rice cultivation

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ABSTRACT

Indragiri Hilir is rice production center in Riau Province. The rice productivity in this regency is around 3.9 ton/ha. Since 2017, Riau AIAT has introduced jarwo super rice system as new technology in rice cultivation. This study aims to get the information on rice production in the integration of duck and jarwo super rice system compared to the existing technology. The study was conducted in Kempas Jaya Village, Indragiri Hilir Regency, Riau Province from January-August 2018. Batang Piaman was chosen as suitable variety with farmer preference. There were three technologies applied in this study, A: farmer's technology, B: jarwo super rice system technology and C: integration of duck and jarwo super rice system technology. In integration of duck and jarwo super rice system technology, farmers have 136 ducks that consist of 16 males duck and 120 females duck herder at 1 ha of rice field. The result showed that the highest rice production was found in C: integration of duck and jarwo super rice system technology (7.40 ton/ha), while the rice production in B: jarwo super rice system technology was 6.04 ton/ha and the rice production in A: farmer's technology was 5.10 ton/ha. Based on field observations, there are some advantages when farmer herder ducks in the rice field, (1) provide additional fertilizer from duck droppings, (2) reduce weed and plant pest populations, (3) decrease pesticide used and (4) stimulate rice growth. Referring to this study, combination of duck and jarwo super rice system on rice cultivation has proven decrease production cost, enhance rice production and recommended environmental friendly technology.

Keywords : *duck, jarwo super rice system, integration, environmental friendly technology, rice production.*

INTRODUCTION

The problems in rice cultivation in Indragiri Hilir regency are low rice production due to pests and weed problems. Furthermore, uncertified seed usage, rice fields categorized as tidal land and limited understanding of farmers about cultivation system also contributed to low productivity of rice. Based on the Statistic of Riau Province (2017), the rice productivity in this regency is around 3.9 ton/ha and categorized as low productivity compared to other

regencies.

In 2017, Riau AIAT has introduced jarwo super rice system to the farmers. This technology increases rice production in this regency until 11 t/ha. Nevertheless, it quiet depends on the chemical substances to control pest and weed problems, and also immense utilization of an-organic fertilizer to stimulate rice growth. An alternative technology to minimize the use of the chemical material in rice cultivation system is by raising duck in the rice field.

Lu et al. (2005) reported that the rice-duck cultivation system is an appropriate technology to reduce chemical substances usage and it has been environmentally friendly farming technology which has been accepted in Asia and Pacific. Moreover, Wang et al. (2003) also reported that rice-duck complex ecosystem can improve the environment by reducing the effect of conventional rice system and environmental costs in rice production.

In this system, duck plays an important role. Duck is considered as pest and weed control by consuming them (Li et al., 2004). Furthermore, Long et al. (2013) reported that the rice-duck cultivation system decreases the use of pesticides, herbicides, and fertilizer. Additionally, duck droppings serve as organic fertilizer to support the rice growth, thus it reduces the application of an organic fertilizer. Besides that, duck also plows the soil in the rice field, thus it improves soil properties, and it will enhance the rice growth. In accordance with the research by Yu et al. (2004) that released the rice-duck cultivation system can cause reinforcement of rice growth due to duck activity. Finally, duck paddling overcomes the methane and nitrous oxide problem, which are the contributors to the greenhouse effect.

This study aims to get the information on rice production in the integration of duck and jarwo super rice system compared to the existing technology.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in Kempas Jaya Village, Indragiri Hilir Regency, Riau Province from January-August 2018. The rice cultivation system refers to jarwo super rice system technology; (1) Batang Piaman as chosen superior variety, (2) Legowo 2:1 planting system (3) Agrimeth as organic fertilizer which applied to the rice seeds, (4) M-Dec as bio-decomposer which applied at first soil tillage, (5) Manure application, (6) Urea and NPK Phonska application, and (6) Pest and disease controlled using bio-protector.

The duck was Pitalah duck, a local variety from West Sumatera. It was 4 months old when herder in the rice field. The additional feed was consists of concentrate N544 and husk. In the integration of duck and jarwo super rice

system technology, farmers have 136 ducks that consist of 16 males duck and 120 females duck herder at 1 ha of rice field.

There were three technologies applied in this study, A: farmer's technology, B: jarwo super rice system technology and C: integration of duck and jarwo super rice system technology.

The cultivation stages were: (1) Nursery : rice seed was saturated for 24 hours, then mixed with Agrimeth and then spread the rice seeds on the nursery plot, (2) Land preparation by cleaning the land from weeds, trees, etc then plowing the soil, (3) Organic fertilizer application from cow manure around 2 ton/ha, (4) Bio-decomposer application 4 kg/ha for straw decomposition, (5) Planting by using Legowo 2:1 system and planting distance 25 x 12.5 x 40 cm and the seedling age were 18 days after seedling, (6) Duck released 15 days after planting (7) Weeding by using manual technology and herbicide, (8) Fertilization by using Urea 200 kg/ha and NPK Phonska 300 kg/ha, (9) Pest and disease control, and (10) Harvest when 90-95% rice grain was ripen.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The result showed that the highest rice production was found in C: integration of duck and jarwo super rice system technology (7.40 ton/ha), while the rice production in B: jarwo super rice system technology was 6.04 ton/ha and the rice production in A: farmer's technology was 5.10 ton/ha (Picture 1).

Picture 1. Rice production (ton/ha)

Based on Picture 1, the integration of duck in the rice field increases the rice production. This similar to the result of Mofidian and Sadeghi (2015), the presence of ducks in a rice field enhance the grain yield around ten percent and consequently it increases farmer's income and also reduction of using agricultural pesticides and protecting the environment. Other studies in integrated duck and rice farming also showed increasing of yield and yield

components (Furuno, 2001; Kishida, 1996; Hossain et al., 2004; Hossain et al., 2005; Ahmad et al., 2004; Wang et al., 2003; Yu et al., 2005).

The increasing of rice production in the integration of duck and jarwo super rice system probably because some reasons. Firstly, duck droppings become additional fertilizer for the rice growth, thus it increases the soil fertility and provides nutrient that needed by the rice plants. Secondly, duck activity and pecking the soil cause mudding water, thus it increases oxygenating in soil and helps farmers in weeding the rice field. Thirdly, duck consumes pests that become a problem in rice cultivation. Reducing the pest population that ingests by ducks will decrease the probability of yield loss.

CONCLUSIONS

This study searched the information about rice production in the integration of duck and jarwo super rice system compared to the existing technology (jarwo super rice system and farmer's technology). The result showed that the integration of duck and jarwo super rice system has a better rice production in Kempas Jaya Village. However, further study is needed to find out the better technology of integration of duck and jarwo super rice system that suitable for all condition by changing the treatment such as the location, number of duck, rice variety and duck variety.

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